

IAM community diagnostic assessment protocol

Version: 1.0

Contact details:

- Mark Dekker (mark.dekker@pbl.nl)
- Mathijs Harmsen (mathijs.harmsen@pbl.nl)
- Elmar Kriegler (kriegler@pik-potsdam.de)

To keep updated on this work, please subscribe to the mailing list of the IAMC SWG on diagnostics and evaluation. See [this link](#) for more information.

1. Motivation.....	2
2. Organization.....	3
2.1 Scope and outcomes.....	3
2.2 Types of models.....	3
2.3 Timeline.....	4
2.4 Terms of submission.....	4
3. Practical guidelines.....	5
3.1 General comments.....	5
3.2 Preparations per modelling team.....	5
3.3 How does one submit and view model output?.....	6
4. Diagnostic scenario setup.....	7
4.1 Scenario overview.....	7
4.2 General specifications.....	11
5. Diagnostic indicators.....	12
6. Examples of diagnostic analyses.....	14
References.....	16

1. Motivation

With the increasingly larger role of IAMs in climate policy research and support, there is a strong need for actions that maximize model transparency and understanding. For academics and policy makers it is critically important to thoroughly understand how models behave and relate to each other, as well as to have an understanding of how IAM structure and assumptions affect IAM behavior. This goes beyond simply comparing projections of different models across scenarios, but rather exploring specific model dynamics that lead to a given scenario's result. Model diagnostic exercises provide a key function in this respect. They assess IAM responses in simple, stylized scenarios to characterize model behaviour. To easily compare the model responses, they are expressed in so-called *diagnostic indicators* – general and summarizing variables, based on IAM outputs, that reflect a certain aspect of model behavior. This approach is analogous to diagnostics for climate models, where a set of standard indicators exists that classify behavior (e.g. climate sensitivity or transient climate response).

To date, diagnostic efforts in the IAM community have been on an ad hoc basis¹⁻⁷. Examples are Gaskins et al. (1993)⁸, Weyant (2004⁹ and 2010¹⁰) (Energy Modelling Forum, or EMF), van Vuuren et al. (2009)⁴, Wilkerson et al. (2015)¹¹, Kriegler et al. (2015)⁵, Harmsen et al. (2021)¹² and Dekker et al. (2023)⁷, based on work in the AMPERE, ADVANCE, NAVIGATE and ECEMF projects. These papers, each building on the previous, developed an expanding set of diagnostic scenarios and indicators. However, there has not been convergence towards one standardized approach on a community-wide scale. With this protocol, we propose a standardized diagnostic assessment approach for the full IAM community, with the aim of using it as standard practice in all future (and potentially currently existing) IAM and scenario-based projects, to routinely assess model behavior in future projects. This helps to allow for comprehensive and consistent model comparisons, also for model versions in time.

This document presents a proposal for an IAM community assessment protocol that aims to provide a standardized approach for IAM diagnostics across the community. We are asking interested modelling teams to implement the protocol and submit diagnostic runs from their model to help us vet the protocol during a pilot phase. Diagnostic runs should be submitted to a dedicated IIASA-hosted database for this exercise (link will follow). The timeline for this is described in the next section. The submitted runs will be analyzed and compared by the contact persons together with the IAMC Scientific Working Group on Model Diagnostics and Evaluation and participating modelling teams. The aim is (i) to evaluate after if the protocol is fit for purpose as a community standard and adjust it as needed, based on the experiences during this exercise and (ii) to write a diagnostic model comparison paper based on the submitted runs, documenting the response patterns of the most recent batch of IAMs. The SWG aims to decide on a community standard for the model diagnostic protocol by the end of 2026 based on the outcome of this pilot phase.

2. Organization

2.1 Scope and outcomes

PBL will take the lead in the analyses, and analysts from national teams will be invited to participate in analyzing national diagnostics. Results can be published on the IAMC wiki and in scientific papers (e.g. combined with respective project scenario study). The simple diagnostic runs would require relatively little extra time, while participating teams can benefit from the diagnostic exercise to understand how model differences lead to differences in scenario results in the context of model comparison exercises. It is possible to largely automate the diagnostic analyses (the code for the indicators and figures is available and there is potential to work on further automation).

The test-case project will give us insights into questions such as:

- How do the results compare to earlier studies?
- Are there any suggested final changes to the protocol?
- How to maintain indicator and figure scripts and protocols?
- What are the best visualisations of the results?
- How to organise and consolidate the future procedure? How, and under which circumstances, can current projects join this effort? For example, which models will be included?
- Should we define a reference ensemble to compare the results to?
- What are the options to automate the diagnostics exercises via the IIASA scenario explorers?

2.2 Types of models

The initial focus of the diagnostic assessment will be on global models. Current multi-model IAM projects that are planning or preparing IAM model intercomparison studies are particularly encouraged to take up the diagnostic scenarios and participate in the pilot phase with the full set of models included in the project. However, national modelling teams are welcome to join. Like for global models, national and regional data will be stored in the dedicated database. Where possible, we will include national and regional data already in the first analysis (in 2026), and most definitely in subsequent analyses. This will be further discussed with any national models that participate and be based on how many regional/national models participate.

A key ingredient of the diagnostic scenarios (Tab. 1) is the globally uniform carbon price. If your model is not able to incorporate or translate a proxy for this, it will be difficult for you to participate. In case of doubt, please contact us.

All participating teams have to agree with the terms of submission (see annex 1). The main reasons for the agreement are to ensure confidentiality concerning preliminary and unpublished results, and publication rights after a cut-off date.

2.3 Timeline

We are proposing the following timeline:

Date	Step
End Feb 2026	Draft community-standard protocol published for review
15 March 2026	Deadline for comments
Mid-April 2026	Online document published Full database accessible only for SWG board and analysts
1 Sep 2026	Submission deadline for pilot phase
Fall 2026	Evaluation of pilot phase Update protocol Start writing community paper Full database access for registered users from all teams
1 Feb 2027	Community-standard diagnostics protocol published Community paper published Database public
Post-2027	We aim for this exercise to be recurring, so that model diagnostics are kept up-to-date with model development. How this recurring process looks will be discussed once this first pilot exercise is finished.

2.4 Terms of submission

Scenario authors retain full rights on their own sharing and use of their scenario data. Those rights will not be affected by submission, use and publication of their data in the diagnostics pilot exercise. We foresee a few phases in accessibility of the data.

During the analysis of the scenario data by scenario contributors and the coordinators and analysts of the diagnostics pilot exercise, the submitted preliminary and unpublished data will be kept confidential and will only be accessible to the coordinators and analysts of the exercise and the co-chairs of the SWG on Model Evaluation and Diagnostics. These analysts with access will be asked to sign a confidentiality agreement.

By submitting their scenarios to the IIASA database (link will follow), scenario authors grant the coordinators and analysts the right to analyse their data as part of a diagnostic scenario model intercomparison and to present it at IAMC internal fora, in particular sessions of the SWG on Model Diagnostics and Evaluation. In the fall of 2026 (at IAMC, but also through exchanging paper drafts), preliminary versions of the analysis will be shared and all registered users of the database (see [Database coordination](#)), beyond only the small group of analysts and the SWG board, will be granted access to the database. So, up until fall 2026, the data will remain fully confidential.

Scenario authors retain the right to withdraw their scenario data after submission at any time before 31 December 2026. After 1 January 2027, scenario authors automatically transfer a nonexclusive right to the coordinators and analysts of the diagnostics pilot exercise to publish their submitted scenario data at the time of the publication of the associated paper.

3. Practical guidelines

3.1 General comments

We acknowledge that not all modelling teams can do all scenarios (Table 1), for example when having a particular temporal, sectoral or regional scope (see also 2.2). We encourage all teams to participate in ways you can. Feel free to contact us (see page 1 for contact details) to discuss options in case of doubt.

The diagnostic indicators mentioned in Table 3 require at least the variables stated in [Variable list](#). Also here, not being able to report some of these variables should not prohibit participation. This is not a big problem for the analysis: whenever reporting is missing, these indicators will simply not be computed for your model, but you can participate in other indicator comparisons. Still, we would like to emphasize paying attention to the spreadsheet [Variable list](#) to report as much as possible from this list. Reporting more variables is encouraged because that facilitates future subsequent analysis beyond the indicators.

Below, in section 3.2, you see that we ask for main points of contact and github usernames. That does not have to be one single person - in fact it could be advantageous to have a few experts involved. The submitted contacts are not necessarily linked to author lists of potential future scientific publications. When papers are involved, we will take stock of which teams participate and those teams will all have a certain number of authors they can list. In other words, there is no restriction or commitment made when sending the contact information below concerning papers.

3.2 Preparations per modelling team

We ask all participating modelling teams to either send the following information to Mark Dekker (mark.dekker@pbl.nl) and Mathijs Harmsen (mathijs.harmsen@pbl.nl):

- General details:
 - **Full model name**
 - **Model versions** you aim to incorporate in this analysis. This could involve multiple versions.
 - **Institute**
 - **Main contacts** (could be multiple)
 - **Main contact email addresses**
 - In case you are not already on the [IAMC wiki](#), please send us:
 - **Reference to model documentation**
 - **Regional coverage** (global / regional / national, and whether it is single-region or multiple-region model)

- Details for the scenario database:
 - **IIASA database user account name** (for those from your team that you want to submit scenarios to the database). If you do not have such an account, please contact Lisah Ligonio at IIASA (ligono@iiasa.ac.at).
 - **Github usernames** of a few of your colleagues, if you want to see or contribute to the forked and IIASA database workflow repositories. This is not strictly necessary.
 - If you are not already part of the **common-definitions** repository, if the mappings and definitions there are not up-to-date, or if you do not know what this is, please send us the following information:
 - **List of native model regions**, including exact naming of the regions, as well as what countries the native model regions comprise. This is ideally delivered in the form of a YAML file with a particular format. An example can be found [here](#).
 - **List of mappings between native model regions and common regions** such as R5, G20, EU or the world. This is ideally in the form of a YAML file with a particular format. An example can be found [here](#).

After this is sent to us, we will build in the scenario database to recognize your model and your model regions, and give the appropriate users submission rights.

When provided with your Github usernames, we can add you to a Github team (see [here](#)). The model registration details will be implemented in a forked Github repository by PBL colleagues (see [here](#)), before pulling into the final IIASA workflow that can be viewed [here](#). Only users that have provided their Github usernames can of course access these links.

3.3 How does one submit and view model output?

When provided with your IIASA database account names, we can give you access to the Scenario Explorer, where you can do the scenario submissions. It can be found [here](#) (login and registration required). Under 'scenario submission' (top tab), one can upload model output in the form of spreadsheets in IAMC format (see more information [here](#)).

Own submitted scenarios can always be viewed on the IIASA Scenario Explorer, but submissions from other teams will only become visible in the fall of 2026 (see timeline in section 2.3).

4. Diagnostic scenario setup

4.1 Scenario overview

The diagnostic exercise will require teams to run a set of seven, easy-to-implement, stylised carbon price scenarios that can be compared to a model's default current policy reference scenario (CP, formerly also called NPi, or 'implemented national policies', see Table 1 for further specification). To serve the objective of characterizing policy-relevant response patterns among a broad range of models, the scenarios and indicators (see section below) should meet the following criteria:

- Identification of heterogeneity in model responses (it should allow for an assessment of factors that differ across models).
- Diagnosis of relevant features for climate policy analysis.
- Applicability to diverse models (all models should be able to represent the mechanisms of interest).
- Accessibility and ease of use (diagnostic scenario settings should be easy to implement).
- Standardization and comparability between diagnostic studies (the setup of the diagnostic assessment should remain set over time).
- Precision/quantifiability (the main analysis is based on one target year and core scenario, allowing for a clear comparison across models).

See Table 1 for the scenario overview. There are five mandatory scenarios: one with a linearly increasing carbon price at different levels (C400-lin), two with an exponentially growing carbon price (C160-gr5 and C80-gr5), one carbon price shock scenario, which can be used to assess the models' inertia (C0to400-lin) and the reference scenario (CP). C400-lin can be considered the main diagnostic scenario, as it provides the key values used for model (version) comparisons (as in the ECEMF project, published in Dekker et al., 2023). It has a higher carbon price than in earlier studies, which is more in line with carbon prices commonly reported in deep mitigation scenarios. The carbon price is also linearly increasing, leading to a higher short-term impact, and having the advantage of easy implementation. The other scenarios (except for C0to400-lin) are used to check if model behaviour and relative model differences are significantly different under different conditions. In addition, there are optional scenarios, where the C400-lin carbon price path is combined with assumptions on limited bioenergy, CCS availability and CDR availability (C400-lin-LimBio and C400-lin-LimCCS, from Dekker et al., 2023, complemented with C400-lin-LimCDR). Two optional scenarios are added for models that represent land-use: C400-lin-Diet, C400-lin-BiodivProt. These are used to assess model behaviour under typical land-use interventions (EAT-Lancet diet and land protection for biodiversity conservation). One additional optional scenario (C400-lin-Policies) is added to explore the role of ambitious non-carbon price-induced policies. Teams are also invited to submit their no-climate-policy baseline scenario (No-Policy). The diagnostic scenarios are constructed with the sole purpose of allowing the academic community to conduct model diagnostics. They are not expected to reproduce current observations or policy settings and are therefore explicitly not intended to provide policy analysis.

Table 1: Scenario overview. See Table 2 and Fig. 1 for the carbon price paths. Carbon prices are given in (2010 US\$ /t CO₂). For models that produce SSP2 scenarios, that should be the default in the scenarios below. SSP variations are strongly encouraged. Models that do not produce SSPs, should submit their default socio-economic pathways (see also section 4.2).

Scenario name	Tier	Characterization	Details
CP	Mandatory	Current policies, reference	The default current climate policy reference scenario(CP). Only implemented policies should be included, not targets that are not supported by policies (e.g. NDC). Climate policies can be explicitly modelled (preferably) or represented by a carbon price. If neither option is available, model teams can use their default No-Policy baseline. If a scenario deviates from CP, a description of the scenario assumptions should be provided.
C400-lin	Mandatory	Linear pricing	For t < 2030: Fix to CP For t in [2030, 2100]: Price(t) = 35 USD + 18.25 USD * (t-2030) (USD400 reached in 2050) After 2030, take C-price from CP if higher than Price(t), until Price(t) becomes higher. Then take Price(t).
C160-gr5	Mandatory	Exponential pricing	For t < 2030: Fix to CP For t in [2030, 2100]: Price(t) = 160 USD * 1.05 ^(t-2030) (USD160 reached in 2050) After 2030, take C-price from CP if higher than Price(t), until Price(t) becomes higher. Then take Price(t).
C80-gr5	Mandatory	Exponential pricing	For t < 2030: Fix to CP For t in [2030, 2100]: Price(t) = 80 USD * 1.05 ^(t-2030) (USD 80 reached in 2050) After 2030, take C-price from CP if higher than Price(t), until Price(t) becomes higher. Then take Price(t).
C0to400-lin	Mandatory	Linear pricing; Shock in price	Follow CP in the short run, but converge to Price(t) = 0 USD right before 2050 For t in [2050, 2100]: price as C400-lin.
C400-lin-LimBio	Optional	Linear pricing; Limiting biomass	Emission prices follow C400-lin. Global primary modern bioenergy supply (from any primary resource) is limited to 100EJ. No constraints on traditional biomass use are applied.
C400-lin-LimCCS	Optional	Linear pricing; Limiting CCS	Emission prices follow C400-lin. Global application of geological Carbon Capture and Storage (including fossil CCS, DACCS and BECCS) is limited to a maximum of 2Gt CO ₂ /yr. The total non-CCS carbon dioxide removal (CDR) should not exceed the total non-CCS CDR level of C400-lin. A margin of 0.5Gt CO ₂ /yr in 2060 is allowed.
C400-lin-LimCDR	Optional	Linear pricing; Limiting CDR	Limited carbon dioxide removal (CDR). Emission prices follow C400-lin. Includes limits from C400-lin-LimBio and C400-lin-LimCCS. In addition: this applies the following limits: 350 Mha for afforestation and reforestation (combined), 0.5 Gt CO ₂ /yr for biochar, 0 Gt CO ₂ /yr for ocean algae, 0.5 Gt CO ₂ /yr for enhanced weathering.
C400-lin-Diet	Optional	Linear pricing; Limiting animal products	Emission prices follow C400-lin. EAT-Lancet 2 diet is implemented from 2025 to 2070. Only suitable for models that represent agriculture, land-use and natural environments.
C400-lin-BiodivProt	Optional	Linear pricing; Land protection	Emission prices follow C400-lin. Implementing land use protection for biodiversity of 30% from 2030 to 2100 in line with the GBF (Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework). Only suitable for models that represent agriculture, land-use and natural environments.

C400-lin-Policies	Optional	Linear pricing; additional mitigation policies	Emission prices follow C400-lin; plus all non-carbon price-related policies / modeling switches that a modeling team usually uses in “lowest stabilization” (e.g., 1.5°C) scenarios (teams need to provide the details of the original scenario). This would not mean harmonizing those policies, but just take the current “default” from that team. Comparing this run to the C400-lin would give an idea of how important additional policies are for a specific model/team.
No-Policy	Optional	No Policy baseline	Counterfactual scenario with no climate policies and no carbon prices.
*-SSPX	Optional (strongly encouraged)	Any	For any of the scenarios in the above (notably the mandatory ones), teams are encouraged to submit alternative SSP variations (other than SSP2), named *-SSPX, where * is the normal scenario name, and X is the SSP identifier. Note that in that case, teams need to submit the reference scenario and one or more of the pricing scenarios. For the default (SSP2-or similar-based) scenarios, no -SSPX suffix should be added.

Figure 1: Carbon eq. prices in the carbon price scenarios (2010 US\$ /t CO₂).

Table 2: Carbon eq. prices in the carbon price scenarios (2010 US\$ /t CO₂). Note that price paths start in 2030, which is 10 years later than in previous diagnostics studies. Prices in the main scenario are in line with common prices in deep mitigation scenarios. C400-lin and C80-gr5 have been the main scenarios in Dekker et al. (2023) and Harmsen et al. (2021), allowing for a comparison with previous studies.

	2030	2040	2050	2060	2070	2080	2090	2100
C400-lin (main)	35	218	400	582	765	947	1130	1312
C160-gr5	60	98	160	261	425	692	1126	1835
C80-gr5	30	49	80	130	212	346	563	917
C0to400-lin			400	582	765	947	1130	1312

4.2 General specifications

We aim to make diagnostic runs standard practice for each global IAM-based project. The model should be the same version as used in the respective project, where the diagnostic run is performed. In addition, teams can submit other model versions. These should be unaltered versions that were used and documented earlier or elsewhere.

Time horizon: We use a benchmark year for the assessment that lies 30 years after the start year of the carbon price path. The start year is now set at 2030, and the benchmark year is 2060. Note that this is 10 years later than the carbon price paths in the last diagnostics studies (!). In future studies (after 2030), start- and benchmark years will be reset to the nearest rounded decades (i.e., the next start- and benchmark years are 2040 and 2070) to accommodate models with 10-year time steps. For models with a 2100-time horizon, scenarios run up to 2100. Models with a shorter time horizon may report up to their final year. Shorter time spans are okay, but note that the benchmark year of 2060 is crucial to our analysis.

Regional scale: A main part of this diagnostic assessment will be conducted at the global level, because of comparability with previous studies and representation across most models. As mentioned in section 2.2, we do encourage regional and even national outputs to be submitted if teams find ways to translate the scenarios to their more refined scale. Hence, though dependent on the population of the database, we do aim to have another part of the analysis dedicated to regional scales. Note that in all scenarios, there is one uniform global carbon price assumed, i.e., the same carbon price should be applied to all regions. At all times, full regional reporting is encouraged (see sections 2.2 and 3.2) to have projections on as many scales as possible, for this or subsequent analyses to come.

Socio-economic assumptions: For models that have produced SSP2, all scenarios should be based on SSP2 (for a definition, see [Riahi et al.\(2017\)](#)). For other models, scenarios should be produced with the default model settings. If the default model settings diverge significantly from SSP2, teams need to let us know and share details on the socio-economic drivers. Teams have the option to submit scenarios based on other SSPs than SSP2. This can be done by adding a dash and the SSP name as a suffix after the model's name, e.g. IMAGE34-SSP3.

Sectoral coverage and reporting: Teams should report key emission and activity data for all sectors that are represented in the models and emission data for all represented GHGs. Teams should use their default emission metric (typically the default 100-year GWP; AR4, AR5, AR6).

Currency: All carbon Price scenarios are specified in and should be reported in 2010 US dollars per ton of CO₂. Models using a different base year for US dollars should apply an appropriate deflator to convert the carbon prices to the given base year. We suggest: https://www.bls.gov/data/inflation_calculator.htm

Foresight: Intertemporal optimisation models should turn off foresight to avoid anticipation of future carbon price shocks in the diagnostic scenarios.

5. Diagnostic indicators

Table 3 provides an overview of the proposed indicators. Indicators are determined in the year 2060, unless otherwise specified. The equations and rationale behind the indicators are further described in Dekker et al. (2023) and Harmsen et al. (2021). Figures 2 and 3 (below in this section) provide an example of the visualization of the model comparisons for the key indicators in the two papers (Figure 2: RAI indicator from Harmsen et al. and Figure 3: model fingerprints (representing multiple indicators) from Dekker et al.).

Table 3: Key diagnostic indicators.

Key indicator	Represents
Relative Abatement Index (RAI)	% abatement relative to baseline
Carbon Intensity (CI) reduction	CI compared to 2020
Energy Intensity (EI) reduction	EI compared to 2020
Carbon capture and storage (CCS)	Absolute value in benchmark year
Non-CO ₂ mitigation (NC)	Non-CO ₂ reduction as share of total GHG reduction
Transformation Index (TI)	Overall transformation speed energy system (0-2 index)
Inertia_1	# of years before 66% of CO ₂
Inertia_2 (Inertia Timescale, IT)	Cumulative difference in emissions between C400-lin and C0to400-lin over 2040-2100 period, divided by emission gap in 2040 (in years)
Electrification	% electricity in total final energy, per sector
Primary energy mix	Share per source (e.g. solar, wind, fossils etc.)
Cost per Abatement Value (CAV)	Policy costs / marginal costs
Land use CO ₂ emissions	Cumulative AFOLU CO ₂ emissions (from land use, land-use change and agriculture) in the 2030-2060 period
Land-based CDR	Cumulative land-based sequestration (2030–2060), e.g. from AR
Non-CO ₂ AFOLU mitigation (NC AFOLU)	Non-CO ₂ AFOLU reduction as share of total AFOLU GHG reduction
Land Use (LU)	Share of total land cover in 2060 for Cropland (food&feed, bioenergy), Pasture, Forest, Other natural land and Urban land
Crop Yield Change	% change in crop yield (2020–2060) $(Yield_{2060} - Yield_{2020}) / Yield_{2020} * 100$
Agricultural production	Total, food/feed crops, energy crops, livestock products
Food availability	Total, crops, livestock products
If sufficient variable reporting: Food Expenditure Share or Food prices	Affordability of food / food economy

Notes:

- As CP scenarios can differ considerably across models, the aim has been to formulate more indicators as part of the base year, e.g. EI and CI. The CI indicator has therefore become very similar to the Fossil Fuel Reduction indicator from Harmsen et al., which is now excluded here.
- All indicators are defined such that values are independent of the model ensemble (i.e. defined based on single-model outcomes only). In addition, we show how models compare to the model ensemble (using only the latest model versions, to avoid a bias towards models with many participating versions). Both absolute and model-relative values are relevant and should be provided. Depending on the indicator, either absolute or relative can be most interesting. Absolute values don't change over time and will be well documented.
- More indicators can easily be generated using the fingerprint analysis from Dekker et al. When running the optional scenarios, it is also possible to create a fingerprint analysis that shows the spread across scenarios for each model

6. Examples of diagnostic analyses

By means of illustration, below, we show two analyses that were performed in the last five years on this topic, making use of most of the diagnostic indicators and similar-type diagnostic scenarios as defined in sections 3 and 4.

Figure 2: Example analysis: relative abatement index (RAI) in 2050 from Harmsen et al., (2021) Left: (global) relative abatement index (RAI) in 2050 for ~50 and 130 \$/tCO₂. Coloured lines represent latest model versions. Right: RAI value for 130 \$/tCO₂ based on default model run. Stars represent the latest model versions. Models are grouped based on type

Figure 3: Example analysis: Model ‘fingerprints’ from Dekker et al., (2023), representing IMAGE (a), REMIND (b), MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM (c) and WITCH (d) models for Europe in 2050. The axis for each indicator ranges between the ensemble median (η) \pm two standard deviations (σ). These medians and standard deviations are computed from the full ensemble, that is, the eight models and nine linearly increasing-price scenarios (excluding the current-policies scenarios), and the coloured shaded scenario ranges are for each individual model indicated by the panel titles. Data close to the centre reflect below-median results. Data towards the outer ring reflect above-median results.

References

- 1 Gaskins, D. W. & Weyant, J. P. Model Comparisons of the Costs of Reducing CO2 Emissions. *American Economic Review* **82**, 318–323 (1993).
- 2 Weyant, J. P. EMF-19 alternative technology strategies for climate change policy. *Energy Economics* **26**, 501–755 (2004).
- 3 Weyant, J. *Program on Integrated Assessment Model Development, Diagnostics and Inter-Model Comparison (PIAMDDI): an overview, IAMC Annual Meeting, 2010*, http://www.globalchange.umd.edu/iamc_data/iamc2010/PIAMDDI_Overview.pdf, 2010).
- 4 van Vuuren, D. P. *et al.* Comparison of top-down and bottom-up estimates of sectoral and regional greenhouse gas emission reduction potentials. *Energy Policy* **37**, 5125–5139 (2009). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2009.07.024>
- 5 Kriegler, E. *et al.* Diagnostic indicators for integrated assessment models of climate policy. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* **90**, 45–61 (2015). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2013.09.020>
- 6 Harmsen, M. *et al.* Integrated assessment model diagnostics: key indicators and model evolution. *Environmental Research Letters* **16** (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abf964>
- 7 Dekker, M. M. *et al.* Identifying energy model fingerprints in mitigation scenarios. *Nature Energy* **8**, 1395–1404 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-023-01399-1>
- 8 Gaskins, D. W. & Weyant, J. P. Model Comparisons of the Costs of Reducing CO2 Emissions. *The American Economic Review* **83**, 318–323 (1993).
- 9 Weyant, J. P. EMF-19 alternative technology strategies for climate change policy *Energy Economics* **26**, 501–515 (2004). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2004.04.019>
- 10 Weyant, J. Program on integrated assessment model development, diagnostics and inter-model comparison (PIAMDDI): an overview. *IAMC Annual Meeting, 2010* (2010).
- 11 Wilkerson, J. T., Leibowicz, B. D., Turner, D. D. & Weyant, J. P. Comparison of integrated assessment models: Carbon price impacts on U.S. energy. *Energy Policy* **76**, 18–31 (2015). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2014.10.011>
- 12 Harmsen, M. *et al.* Integrated assessment model diagnostics: key indicators and model evolution. *Environmental Research Letters* **16**, 054046 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abf964>